

DIGITAL PRESERVATION REPOSITORY AS A DISASTER MANAGEMENT SOLUTION

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Abstract – Disaster planning for digital collections has unique challenges. This preliminary research begins to examine how institutional members of the Academic Preservation Trust (APTrust) view the consortium in the disaster management landscape for their digital collections. The researchers conducted interviews with two staff members from three different APTrust member institutions. They asked about the institution's own disaster management strategies for digital collections as well as how they wanted to do joint disaster planning with the consortium.

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I. INTRODUCTION/LITERATURE REVIEW

Disaster management remains an evergreen issue in library and information science. With the ever increasing number of digital collections, disaster management for them is also an ever-evolving topic that deserves further attention. There are unique technological and logistical challenges for the disaster management of digital collections as compared to that of analog collections. Digital fragility continues to be a barrier in digital preservation. Preserving analog collections can be more hands off, digital collections require more hands-on care during their preservation lifecycle [1], [2]. Underlying assets have limited lifecycles, requiring regular migration to retain access to the content within. Technology evolves rapidly. There is

the risk that support ends for format types and interoperability in the systems storing the data.

One common challenge to digital preservation is how as more higher ed institutions move to cloud based systems for IT infrastructure, digital collections management changes. This can be complicated by the fact that higher education, along with their associated libraries, can be slower to adopt newer technologies and systems. Obstacles to innovation and cloud might be staff readiness, initial investment requirements, or fears about vendor viability [3]. When the Academic Preservation Trust, a preservation consortium, was established, members were concerned about public cloud viability as a long term business model. The initial system designs were constrained to using legacy style architecture, with an exit strategy to a traditional local datacenter implementation [4]. This slowed innovation, though a cloud-native design was fully adopted.

A side effect of slower technology adoption is the hampering of practicing modern IT management processes, improved Cybersecurity, and effective technology governance. For other industries, public and private, there is a robust practice of risk management and disaster management. There are multiple organizations dedicated to developing standards of disaster management, technology governance and security, such as the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) and

the International Organization for Standards (ISO). There are also organizations such as ISC2, the ITIL Foundation and SANS that focus on teaching and developing the practices of risk management, business continuity, and disaster recovery. The combination of slower technology adoption as well as modern IT management practices can leave digital collections particularly vulnerable. One of the ways in which academic libraries can address these challenges is by joining a digital preservation consortium and/or digital preservation services to do joint digital preservation with other similar organizations. For the purposes of this paper, we focus on one digital preservation consortium: APTrust.

The Academic Preservation Trust (APTrust) is a consortium of higher education libraries and memory institutions dedicated to preserving the cultural and scholarly record [5]. APTrust achieves this mission with its membership through a variety of shared resources and activities. A key offering are the custom developed preservation services where members may deposit their digital collections and content. These are 100% cloud based and backed by regionally diverse cloud storage. Recognized standards such as ISO16363 and the OAIS guidelines are followed for the packaging, tracking and the storing of digital content [6]. Additionally, APTrust provides a community for members where they share knowledge and strategies, and support each other in developing new workflows and processes. This includes work on shared objectives within the wider preservation community, such as preserving the cultural record for indigenous communities. Given the diversity of the membership in size of organization and resourcing, APTrust provides a rich community from which to initially explore the challenges for Disaster Management and Disaster Recovery within the preservation community.

In recent years, two APTrust members had to do large scale restorations, drawing on the repositories

and/or expertise of APTrust. One case involved North Carolina State University in 2021. An accidental deletion required a restore of a total of 35TBs of data, 16TB of which had to be restored from their APTrust repos [7]. After six weeks of coordinated work [8], the data was recovered to the master copy locations with 100% percent success. This highlights the significance of disaster management with disaster recovery when addressing growing threats for digital collections.

Risks from cyberattacks have grown significantly for higher education and libraries recently. In 2023, ransomware attacks - attacks where a bad actor seeks to ransom an organization by encrypting their data to prevent access until the organization pays to release it - surged from 129 in 2022 to 265 in 2023 on k-12 and higher ed [9]. This represented a 105% increase, higher than the 68% increase in attacks across all sectors in 2023 [9]. The Rhysida ransomware attack on the British Library in 2023 demonstrates the significant impact from such an attack, but also serious risks libraries face due to a chronic lack of funding, especially for IT and Cybersecurity [10]. As Houghton et al. found in their article *The 2023 Rhysida Ransomware Attack of the British Library*, "The most crucial element was undoubtedly the inadequate in-house IT expertise due to poor funding priorities" [10]. However, the Charlotte Mecklenburg Library and Mecklenburg County avoided paying a \$23,000 ransom because they were able to rebuild their impacted systems from backups [11]. This offers more evidence that disaster management plans can offer substantial risk mitigation for digital collections.

Natural disasters also represent multiple threats to digital as well as analog collections. In 2022 flooding from the Kentucky River in Whitesburg, KY, seriously damaged the Appalshop cultural center which focuses on the cultural art and record of Appalachia [12]. Wildfires in California have threatened libraries from the Reagan Presidential Library in 2019, to the Pacific Palisades library being destroyed in the 2025 California Palisades fire. The

wide areas and speed with which these wildfires spread indicate multi-regional strategies are critical for disaster management. Similar risks exist with the widespread damage from storms such as Hurricane Helene in 2024. Modeling suggests that climate change is worsening these impacts with the NOAA predicting an increase of Category 4 and 5 hurricanes with wetter storms estimated to deposit up to 15% more precipitation [13].

We, Ruffner and Runyon, have created an Incident Management plan for APTrust, combining our complementary expertise in IT and archives. We are invested in further expanding disaster management for the consortium.

We began researching to elucidate how members approach disaster management for digital collections with APTrust, especially how disaster planning within their institution does or does not involve APTrust.

II. METHODOLOGY

We interviewed three different institutions from APTrust: Institution 1, Institution 2, and Institution 3. We solicited the APTrust member list to find one small, one medium, and one large institution for the institutional interviews. For each interview, we included two staff members at each institution for a one hour Zoom interview in March of 2025. Our questions touched on disaster management for digital collections at those specific institutions, digital preservation procedures and staffing at said institutions, and how the institutions used APTrust for disaster management. We deliberately chose to anonymize the institutions interviewed and not provide more in-depth details about their technical environments so as to not make them potential targets for cyber security attacks.

III. DISCUSSION

The interviews proved fruitful and brought out the unique positionalities of the institutions while also exploring themes common across them.

APTrust is a place to seek guidance on common digital preservation challenges, both formally and informally. As one of our interviewees put it, APTrust provides the “stuffs” of digital preservation as in the

tools, opportunities to skill build, and community to consult colleagues on digital preservation challenges. Interviewees from other institutions also mentioned speaking with colleagues at other APTrust member institutions to brainstorm digital preservation concerns.

APTrust provides a mature partner as part of a Disaster Management plan or strategy, especially when considering the toolset and preservation storage options. The ‘Standard’ storage offering provides two complete copies of a single object preserved across two different US regions and in two different S3 storage types, to be used if one copy fails, or to restore local files. There are other storage options based on a member’s unique needs or level of maturity. The restore function is implemented by members through the UI, which restores the content to the institution’s unique S3 restoration bucket. APTrust can be more involved for large bulk restoration. The preservation API offers easy options to check APTrust’s fixity checks and checksums on files to compare with local copies and detect local failures; APTrust runs fixity checks every 180 days on content.

For smaller institutions, these tools and community support are critical. APTrust is THE preservation solution for Institution 2 and Institution 1. Both also mentioned wanting to participate more in tabletop exercises/fire drills, though Institution 2 does already regularly do restorations from APTrust as part of their workflows. Institution 2 has had an all cloud IT infrastructure for several years, an interesting contrast to how many institutions have only recently moved to an all cloud infrastructure.

For Institution 1, disaster management was a primary reason for joining APTrust. One of their staff members referenced the recent Eaton Fire from the 2024 wildfire season in California as a specific flashpoint for thinking about geographically distributed copies of materials, in the event that a national disaster should threaten the Institution 1 campus. Their institution currently has predominantly local storage.

Institution 3 includes APTrust in their preservation ecosystem, but it is not the only solution. Anecdotally, other larger institutions within APTrust have said the same thing. Institution 3 sees APTrust as a more stable partner for digital preservation than

their central IT department and has a more collaborative relationship with APTrust.

All institutions interviewed mentioned specific features of APTrust playing a role in using the service for disaster management. Geographic distribution for files for one, especially for safeguarding against natural disasters (Institution 1) and potential terrorist attacks (Institution 3). Interviewees also brought up APTrust's efforts to meet the NDSA'S Levels of Digital Preservation and OCLC's Trusted Digital Repository standards as a positive for being part of the consortium as a disaster management partner. The staff at Institution 2 brought up a series of APTrust community discussions called Preservation Ecosystems, which started mapping which digital preservation tools APTrust members used and for what purpose. Disaster planning was brought into these discussions as part of the digital collections management lifecycle.

A common theme emerged from all three institutions in that their disaster management plans were either informal, and/or out of date. Institution 1 and Institution 2 had very basic plans that consisted of basic call lists and safety actions, but did not specifically address digital assets. Institution 1 also relies on their central IT for any sort of IT related disaster management because they have no library IT. Institution 3 does have a dedicated library IT for disaster recovery actions, but the disaster management plans are out of date and their digital preservation librarian position is currently vacant. All institutions interviewed wished to have APTrust consult with them on disaster planning, but none had occurred by the date of the interviews. Two of the institutions stated they especially wanted to consult with APTrust for joint disaster management planning after completing ongoing system migrations. They also noted that there were some aspects where the APTrust interface would facilitate disaster management, such as improved reporting of deposits to better track what content is in APTrust. It begs the question, how can collections be restored if the institutions don't know what is there? It is notable that none of the institutions had a similar collaborative relationship with other preservation consortiums, though one was a

member of other digital preservation communities as well.

Despite the different sizes and IT infrastructure, all the institutions interviewed had a lot of overlap in how they approach disaster management for digital collections.

IV. CONCLUSIONS/OPPORTUNITIES FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

This preliminary report begins to elucidate how APTrust member institutions relate to the consortium as a disaster management solution. Although the sample size for this study is small and cannot claim statistical significance, we assert that the similarities between these institutions are evidence that this topic should be explored more, for how digital preservation consortiums can engender collaboration around shared disaster management. It also provides a scaffold for future research into how digital preservation organizations play a role in disaster management. We would like to do more research to see if other institutions who are a part of other digital preservation organizations/consortiums have similar shared custodial relationships to do digital preservation/disaster management for digital collections. We also see opportunities to research the unique precarity of marginalized communities' digital cultural heritage and how their long-term preservation is threatened with climate change, lack of institutional support, cyberattacks, and other risk factors. Multiple APTrust members have discussed supporting associate members of marginalized communities to help safeguard their history, including African American and indigenous communities. We look forward to using the findings of this study to strategize further disaster planning within APTrust and to research more about the topic in the digital preservation field at large.

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